

Corpus Criticorum

A comprehensive bibliography of early modern publications featuring the notion of
Critique on their title pages
(1450-1650)

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Goran Gaber
Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales (LIER-FYT)

Disputatio Medica de crisibus morborum & criticis diebus

Author(s):

Adama, Augustinus Lollius [Praes.]

Groothuis, Rodolphus [Resp.]

Year of publication: 1611

Place of publication: Franeker

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Niedersächsische Staats- und
Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen, Germany

Shelfmark: Coll med 568/1

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_211

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Commonefactio logica

Author(s):

Brawen, Justus

Bodden, Gerhard [ed.]

Gosmann, Bernhard [ed.]

Year of publication: 1643

Place of publication: Rostock

Format: 12°

Location of copy: Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Jena, Germany

Shelfmark: 12 Ph.IV,11(2)

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_018

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Apologia Criticae

Author(s): Campbell, Ninian

Year of publication: 1628

Place of publication: Saumur

Format: 4°

Location of copy: The Sir Duncan Rice Library, University of Aberdeen, Scotland

Shelfmark: pi 807 Cam

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_031

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*In Hippocratis
aphorismos Primi libri.
Critica doctrina per
puncta et quaestiones.*

Author(s): Castelli, Pietro

Year of publication: 1648

Place of publication: Macerata

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Universitätsbibliothek
Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany

Shelfmark: 4 TREW.R 187

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_037

The image was kindly provided by
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De pontificio Gregorii XIII

Author(s): Choppin, René

Year of publication: 1591

Place of publication: Paris

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque nationale de France

Shelfmark: Tolbiac, Rez-de-jardin, LB35-350

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_040

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Pro A. Licinio Archia Oratio

Author(s):

Cicero, Marcus Tullius

Laubanus, Melchior [ed.]

Year of publication: 1614

Place of publication: Brzeg

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Biblioteka Uniwersytecka,
Uniwersytet Wrocławski, Poland

Shelfmark: 372714

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_174

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Biblioteka Uniwersytecka, Uniwersytet Wrocławski.

Discorso astrologico sopra l'anno bisestile 1644

Author(s): Foppa, Carlo Francesco

Year of publication: 1644

Place of publication: Milano

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Biblioteca Nazionale
Braidense, Italy

Shelfmark: VV. 08. 0001/01

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_168

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Biblioteca Nazionale Braidense, Milano, Italy.*

Expositiones suo loco cum textu Auicenne

Author(s):

Foligno, Gentile

Alderotti, Taddeo

Avicenna

Year of publication: 1511

Place of publication: Naples

Format: 2°

Location of copy: University of Chicago Library, USA

Shelfmark: R128.3.A97T53 1511

Corpus Criticorum ID: : CC_BOOK_057

The image was kindly provided by the
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Clio quam ad Sacra Natalitia

Author(s): Freiesleben, Heinrich

Year of publication: 1645

Place of publication: Altenburg

Format: broadsheet

Location of copy: Ratsschulbibliothek
Zwickau, Germany

Shelfmark: 50.1.13.(19)

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_060

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De naturalibus facultatibus libri tres

Author(s):

Galenus, Claudius

Aeginata, Paulus

Winter, Johann [ed.]

Linacre, Thomas [trans.]

Year of publication: 1528

Place of publication: Paris

Format: 8°

Location of copy: The Bodleian Libraries, UK

Shelfmark: Vet. E1 f.6 (Weston Stack)

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_063

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L'Épopée

Author(s): Grandi, Giulio Cesare

Year of publication: 1637

Place of publication: Lecce

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Biblioteca del Seminario
Vescovile di Padova, Italy

Shelfmark: 600.ROSSA.AA.2.-18

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_070

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Disputatio de critica oratoria

Author(s):

Luden, Lorenz [Praes.]

Severini, Andrea [Resp.]

Year of publication: 1627

Place of publication: Greifswald

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Stadtbibliothek Braunschweig,
Germany

Shelfmark: I 149-79

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_155

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Forense Patrocinium

Author(s):

Machelli, Jacopo

Year of publication: 1564

Place of publication: Bologna

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Biblioteca dell' Archiginnasio, Italy

Shelfmark: E16 38

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_186

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Diatribes critica de Maris Balthici nominibus et ostiis

Author(s): Menius, Fredericus

Year of publication: 1634

Place of publication: Tartu

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Tallin University Library,
Estonia

Shelfmark: AL TLU Baltics Collection, XII-947

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_193

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Confronto critico

Author(s): Nali, Marco Antonio

Year of publication: 1643

Place of publication: Padova

Format: 12°

Location of copy: Biblioteca Sormani, Milano,
Italy

Shelfmark: E VET 322

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_116

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In figuram dierum criticorum breuis ac familiaris explanatio

Author(s): Población, Juan Martin

Year of publication: 1535

Place of publication: Paris

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque nationale de France

Shelfmark: General Reference Collection
836.f.23.(3.)

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_135

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Critica Morale

Author(s): Pozzo, Agostino

Year of publication: 1649

Place of publication: Venice

Format: 12°

Location of copy: The British Library, UK

Shelfmark: General Reference Collection
836.f.23.(3.)

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_136

The image was kindly provided by the
British Library.

An die Critico tundenda vena

Author(s):

Richer de Belleval, Martin [Praes.]

Chicoyneau, Michael [Resp.]

Year of publication: 1650

Place of publication: Montpellier

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Biblioteca Nazionale
Braidense, Italy

Shelfmark: A. 03. 00563/002

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_191

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Adversariorum Libri IIII

Author(s): Schriek, Adrian van

Year of publication: 1620

Place of publication: Ypres

Format: 2°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque Mazarine,
France

Shelfmark: 2° 1 A-1

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_200

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Disputatio de diebus criticis prior

Author(s):

Sebisch, Melchior [Praes.]

Ager, Nikolaus [Resp.]

Year of publication: 1626

Place of publication: Strasbourg

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire, Strasbourg, France

Shelfmark: Magasins Joffre M.129.132,1

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_198

The image was kindly provided by the Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire, Strasbourg.

Disputatio de diebus criticis posterior

Author(s):

Sebisch, Melchior [Praes.]

Zschoesy, Melchior [Resp.]

Year of publication: 1626

Place of publication: Strasbourg

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire, Strasbourg, France

Shelfmark: Sezione da recupero M.129.132,2

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_197

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Plautus philologo- criticus hoc est critico- philologica satyra

Author(s): Succov, Henning

Year of publication: 1643

Place of publication: Frankfurt am Main

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque nationale de France

Shelfmark: Tolbiac, Rez-de-jardin, YC-4761

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_159

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Disputatio Critica

Author(s):

Voet, Paulus [Praes.]

Menelaides, Æneas [Resp.]

Year of publication: 1645

Place of publication: Utrecht

Format: 4°

Location of copy: The British Library, UK

Shelfmark: General Reference Collection
836.f.23.(3.)

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_110

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Coronis elogiastica et poetica

Author(s): Gaddi, Jacopo

Year of publication: 1643

Place of publication: Fermo

Format: 4°

Location of copy: Biblioteca Comunale 'Aldo Gabrielli, Ripatransone, Italy

Shelfmark:

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_062

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Le Parnasse ou Le Critique des Poetes

Author(s): La Pinelière, Guérin de

Year of publication: 1635

Place of publication: Paris

Format: 8°

Location of copy: Bibliothèque nationale de France

Shelfmark: Arsenal, RESERVE 8-BL-8647

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_090

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Epistola apologetica

Author(s): Peña, Francisco

Year of publication: 1607

Place of publication: Toledo

Format: 2°

Location of copy: Biblioteca Nacional de España

Shelfmark: VE/1256/2

Corpus Criticorum ID: CC_BOOK_129

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